

D3.1 (M48) - Report Data Stewardship Wizard instance and releases and updates of the knowledge resources for Norwegian users

(an ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR₃ deliverable)

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Context

Context and Background

The main objective of this deliverable was to support Norwegian life science researchers in data management planning by providing tailored resources and tools. Key resources developed and maintained include the Norwegian instance of the [Data Stewardship Wizard \(DSW\)](#), featuring dedicated [knowledge models for life sciences](#). Additional resources include the ELIXIR Research Data Management Kit ([RDMkit](#)), the [ELIXIR Norway RDM lookup service](#) and the national [data management planning knowledge resource](#), which was developed in collaboration with BOTT university libraries. The [DSW knowledge model for BOTT universities](#) further supports local requirements.

Challenges Addressed

This task addressed the challenge of providing a dedicated Data Stewardship Wizard instance and compatible knowledge models tailored to the needs of Norwegian life science users. The goal was to enable researchers to create data management plans (DMPs) that adhere to current best practices and comply with guidelines from [Science Europe](#) and [Horizon Europe](#). Furthermore, the task included the maintenance and continuous updating

of knowledge resources on research data management (RDM), ensuring their relevance for both the Norwegian and broader life science context.

Objectives

The main objectives were the curation and update of guidelines, handbooks, and training materials originating from BioMedData D4.1 and D4.2, and the provision of a sustainable data management planning software platform. The platform was designed to be interoperable with other tools and to facilitate exchange with the international community. The project also aimed to promote exchange at both national and international levels on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data management, and to contribute to the development of best-practice guidelines for FAIR data management.

Delivery

The main activities carried out in this task included the provision and continuous development of a dedicated DSW instance for Norwegian life science users, operated by the ELIXIR network and ELIXIR-CZ, featuring FEIDE login support. Integration with the Norwegian e-Infrastructure for Life Sciences (NeLS) was established, enabling project generation and quota allocation via machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMP).

Regular maintenance releases were performed for export templates, particularly for the [Norwegian life sciences knowledge model](#), with 10 releases since April 2022. In addition, 14 maDMP export template maintenance releases have been issued since 2022, 14 Horizon 2020 export template releases since December 2023, 18 Horizon Europe export template releases since July 2023, and 15 Science Europe export template releases since July 2023.

A forked knowledge model was created from the DSW Life Sciences model to address Norwegian needs, with additional guidance and templates for various subdomains and technologies, based on BioMedData outputs and [cheat sheets](#). A [customized export template](#) was also developed for the national BOTT knowledge model.

Substantial authoring and editorial work was carried out on research-data.no (>230 commits from ELIXIR Norway since January 2024) and RDMkit (>200 commits since April 2022), including content updates, reviews, and editorial contributions.

Ongoing and Upcoming Activities

Ongoing and upcoming activities include the migration of technology- and subdomain-specific templates to the BOTT knowledge model for broader applicability. Further integration of DSW/FAIRwizard with additional systems is planned, such as enabling the incorporation of datasets brokered via NeLS into data management plans for final project reporting and integration with other systems in the Norwegian science administration, including Zenodo deposition and archiving to NVA, integration with SIKT privacy services and the REK approval system.

Outcomes

The main beneficiaries of this task are Norwegian life science researchers and data stewards, as well as Open Science and Research Data Management (RDM) units at BOTT universities and other Norwegian institutions and the main funding bodies, which receive DMPs: the Research Council of Norway and the Regional Health Authorities. DSW Norway is one of the tools [recommended by the Research Council of Norway](#) and currently supports approximately 750 individual users with 1049 projects. RDMkit has reached over 28000 unique users (including more than 1000 from Norway), with around 2400 monthly users in 2026. RDMkit is also [referenced by the Research Council of Norway](#) and in the [Horizon Europe Programme Guide](#). The research-data.no portal has served over 5000 unique users, with about 400 monthly unique users in 2026. Open Science and RDM units at BOTT universities are active users, with other universities in the process of onboarding.

Recommendations

Based on the outcomes, the following actions are recommended:

- Migrate the content from <https://elixir.no/rdm-lookup/> to <https://plan.research-data.no> for improved accessibility and sustainability.
- Migrate life science templates from the 'Life Sciences DSW Knowledge Model – ELIXIR Norway localization' to the 'Norwegian DSW Knowledge Model' to streamline and unify template management.